

Kew monograph 02: More Kew specimens from Nina's product pages

Lemuria¹

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Abstract

We build on the monograph of the Kew dresses with additional descriptions for the Kew dress specimens on Nina Lee's product pages; including the first skirt species description in the entire taxonomy, *Kewisicasa laria*. In total, we describe 21 new species and six new subgenera; and populate the genus *Kewisicasa* with new specimens.

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1 Background

The Kew dress is now perhaps the most extensively-studied sewing pattern in the LCT-01. Earlier in March 2026, we published a 52-page monograph on the Kew dresses, which laid out the structure of Kew dress taxonomy and described over 47 species (Lemuria 2026).

The total count of Kew dress taxa now stands at 1 superfamily (Kewoidea); 5 families (Kewidae, Plesikewidae, Helikewidae, Kewthidae, and Kewcasaceae); 6 subfamilies (Kewbellinae, Kewthinae, Trunkewinae, Helikewinae, Plesikewinae, and Kewasalinae); 2 tribes (Helikewini, Helikewbellini, Kewthini); 19 genera (*Kewplicasa*, *Kewparacasa*, *Kewisicasa*, *Kewbellothea*, *Kewpepla*, *Kewthea*, *Kewthicata*, *Trunkewia*, *Helikewbellia*, *Helikewparabola*, *Helikewplicata*, *Helikewabotonia*, *Helikewisia*, *Kewasalia*, *Florankewia*, *Kewabotonia*, *Kewplicata*, *Kewparabola*, *Kewisia*); 8 subgenera; and 67 species.

Size is typically not considered a relevant morphological character for taxa due to its continuous, non-discrete nature. However, the sale of size ranges of sewing patterns as separate products constitutes discrete phylogenetic information, which is best suited for defining infrageneric taxa. The usage of infrageneric ranks originated in *Heleonora* Lemuria, 2026 (unpublished so far), encompassing the sleeveless variant of the Eleonora by Silver-saga Patterns.

1.1 Taxonomic history

The large amount of Kew dresses on the Internet threatened to inflate the scope of Lemuria (2026) excessively; as such, we enacted a “species freeze” where new Kew specimens would be reserved for subsequent papers. We continue our research into the Kew dress as part of this paper, describing 21 new species, six new subgenera, and one new genus, *Kewisicasa*.

When authoring the Kew monograph, we focused primarily on makes of the pattern in the wild as opposed to official product photos, for a variety of reasons, such as not wanting to have the appearance of a reseller catalog¹, and the anecdotal observation that third parties produce richer documentation than official product pages.

Originally, we were unable to identify the wearers of each holotype specimen beyond their first name. However, on April 3, our lead author decided to include a history of how Chang-Smith developed the expanded size ranges, and in the process, decided also to cite posts by Chang-Smith featuring many of the holotypes on Instagram that

included information on the persons featured. Though not every single person was identifiable due to broken Instagram links or Imginn not having the requested profile, we were able to further confirm some identities by correlating them with filenames from the Nina Lee website.

Timestamps were also updated based on these posts; we inferred the old timestamps from the `v` variable on Shopify CDN images, which likely do not reflect the image’s actual creation date.

1.2 Terminology

The term “expansion” is rather ambiguous in this context, as it can either refer to the Kew dress expansion pack, which adds two skirt options, or to the expanded size range.

Thus, we use four standardized terms for the four Kew patterns.

- Kew 6-20 refers to the “base” Kew pattern, from UK sizes 6 to 20.
- Kew 16-28 refers to the “base” Kew pattern, from UK sizes 16 to 28.
- Kew expansion 6-20 refers to the expansion pack, from UK sizes 6 to 20.
- Kew expansion 16-28 refers to the expansion pack, from UK sizes 16 to 28.

1.3 History of the expansion

The Kew dress’s history is extensively discussed in Lemuria (2026). Here, we focus on Nina Chang-Smith’s expansion of her size range to UK size 28.

The first public evidence that Chang-Smith was working on the expansion came in October 2019, when she posted an advertisement looking for a UK size 20 fit model to review her adjusted base size with, before grading. In the advertisement, Chang-Smith specified a model with a bust of ~116 cm (46 in), waist of ~98 cm (39 in), and hip of ~124 cm (49 in)² (Chang-Smith 2019).

Chang-Smith worked on her expanded ranges in reverse-chronological pattern release order; recruiting testers for the Southbank, Carnaby, and Mayfair in January 2020 (Chang-Smith 2020c); and later in September, the Kew (Chang-Smith 2020a). On February 19, 2021, the Kew 16-28 pattern was released.

¹This concern is a holdover from our internal MediaWiki site, where we embed images more freely than in the *Journal*. The academic paper format of the *Journal* extensively distinguishes it from a reseller listing or catalog.

²Exact measurement methodology unknown. We assume that the waist and hip measurements are that of the body’s circumference. Our lead author is male and does not trust himself to make assumptions regarding bust size measurements.

2 Methods

The lead author conducted his research on a computer running Ubuntu 24.04, with the XFCE desktop environment. He used the SHA2-256 algorithms to compute the cryptographic hashes of the photographic specimens he examined for species descriptions. He used Firefox 139.0.4. His monitor is a 55.8 cm (22 in) wide, 30.48 cm (12 in) tall, 63.5 cm (25 in) diagonal monitor, the NVISION S2515-B 25" IPS with a 100Hz refresh rate. He is not colorblind. He is near sighted and wears glasses.

As our lead author had no Instagram account, he used Imginn, an online service that allows Instagram to be viewed without an account.

Specimens were collected from Nina Lee's product pages on <https://ninalee.co.uk>. All images were in JPG format. The website uses Shopify as its underlying platform and image storage; EXIF metadata is scarce, and this removal is likely consistent with internal Shopify server-side upload processing code. EXIF metadata was checked using ExifTool version 12.76.

```
$ sha256sum --version
sha256sum (GNU coreutils) 9.4
Copyright (C) 2023 Free Software Foundation, Inc.
License GPLv3+: GNU GPL version 3 or later <https://gnu.org/licenses/gpl.html>.
This is free software: you are free to change and redistribute it.
There is NO WARRANTY, to the extent permitted by law.
```

Written by Ulrich Drepper, Scott Miller, and David Madore.

```
$ openssl --version
OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025 (Library: OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025)
$ sha256sum /usr/bin/sha256sum /usr/bin/openssl
f293048f656688883ee919eb3f4b12926aaa13362de0eb6e3b5716b915b18b35 /usr/bin/sha256sum
724acbe911513d13f52bae0b8969b20336cd8618fc67898a6bf7847bf1a270ad /usr/bin/openssl
```

Figure 1: A hash of the sha256sum and openssl utilities on the lead author's computer.

3 Trees

As previously stated in Lemuria (2026), the hybrid phenetic-phylogenetic structure of the LCT-01 causes the Kew dresses to scatter polyphyletically across the tree. The updated Kew trees are presented below.

2.1 lct01-notes

During work on this paper, the author created a new tool that automatically generates Quarto template text from structured YAML data. This allows the data to exist in a structured format for future processing with other systems, and further improves standardization. Descriptions and remarks remain human-written; with less administrative and menial work comes the opportunity for more creative work.

A paper dedicated solely to this software has not been started, but may be authored someday. The tool was developed during the creation of this paper; as such, not all entries were automatically templated. YAML files used to generate some of the template texts are provided with the paper.

2.2 Checksums

The versions of the sha256sum and openssl utilities on his system at the time of the paper are given in the below terminal output:

Figure 2: Overview

Figure 3: Kewcasaceae

Figure 4: Kewthidae

Figure 5: Helikewidae

Figure 6: Kewoidea

4 Descriptions

4.1 Genus *Helikewbellia*

Helikewbellia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Helikewbellia* is characterized by origin from the sleeveless variant of the Kewbello pattern; phenetically, the combination of the Kew sleeveless strappy bodice and Portobello trousers; and the presence of a dorsal medial zipper on the bodice. Bilateral ventral darts present from the third button to the bodice–skirt seam; bilateral sets of three seams at outward flare angle; bilateral pockets.

Remarks: There exist two phylogenetic pathways through which a sleeveless Kewbello may arise; from the Kewbello pattern itself (pathway 1), or an independent recombination of the Kew sleeveless dress bodice and the Portobello trousers, done without referencing the pattern (pathway 2). Pathway 2 remains unattested.

Type species: *Helikewbellia flutteria* (see Section 4.2.2)

4.2 *Helikewbellia* subg. *Ninae*

Helikewbellia subgenus *Ninae* Lemuria, 2026

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Helikewbellia* subg. *Ninae* is defined by having been created by Nina Chang-Smith.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*.

Type species: *Helikewbellia flutteria* (see Section 4.2.2)

4.2.1 *Helikewbellia melalourida*

Helikewbellia melalourida Lemuria, 2026

Holotype: *Nina 90381.248* — Photograph. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewbellia melalourida* wb. Nina, unknown. Angled ventral view. Subject’s arms fully adducted, in pockets; ventral medial button row blends into fabric, visibility impeded. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026e)
- **SHA2-256:** 00d5f66d76582d50e753f55b5b7d5c4f197703d159a0777293de27349064418c
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_black_straps_side_view_pink_background.jpg?v=1722462174
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_black_straps_side_view_pink_background.jpg?v=1722462174

Diagnosis: *Helikewbellia melalourida* is characterized by a fabric with a black background, with white line drawings of houses and palm trees, consistent with upper-class coastal California communities.

Remarks: The description of the fabric as being similar to upper-class coastal California communities may be influenced by the lead author’s knowledge that as of 2026, Nina Chang-Smith has lived in California since 2022.

Etymology: From Latin *melas* (“black”) + Greek λουρίδα (*lourída*, “strap”), referring to the black color of the straps.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Nina 90381.276* — Photograph. EXIF metadata stripped. Dorsal view. Hair positioned ventrally. *Helikewbellia melalourida* wb. Nina, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026e)
 - **SHA2-256:** 22c2db3b17bd839650280e8f4e51a98d75da5021d20c9c5358adc37894a36fa5
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_black_straps_back_view_pink_background.jpg?v=1722462174

- * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_black_straps_back_view_pink_background.jpg?v=1722462174

4.2.2 *Helikewbellia flutteria*

Helikewbellia flutteria Lemuria, 2026

Holotype: *Nina 90387.475* — Photograph. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewbellia flutteria* wb. Nina, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026e)
- **SHA2-256:** c9483d4b827b26e3f9cd41c381380dbe04ca28b2e8ba2ef41ea097d768242c2e
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_yellow_straps_blue_background.jpg?v=1722462244
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_yellow_straps_blue_background.jpg?v=1722462244

Diagnosis: *Helikewbellia flutteria* is characterized by a flutter sleeve, with fabric attached to the lateral sides of the straps; and a fabric with a vague watercolor floral pattern, with a yellow background, with smaller amounts of pale orange and olive green color; and a ventral medial button row of five circular buttons with an interior curved square and four thread holes; and yellow thread.

Remarks: The classification of *Helikewbellia flutteria* may be a useful example in the eventual classification of Lauren Johnson’s flutter Kew dress.

Etymology: From English *flutter*, a word of Germanic origin + *-ia*, for a Latin feel.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Nina 90387.478* — Photograph. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewbellia flutteria* wb. Nina, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:**
 - **SHA2-256:** 87425f5d907e3c01382b563e6e276bd506e838159014d2973a6b9d8fb3e79391
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_yellow_straps_blue_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_yellow_straps_blue_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174

4.3 Genus *Helikewisia*

Helikewisia Lemuria, 2026

See Lemuria (2026).

4.3.1 *Helikewisia roseatulipa*

Helikewisia roseatulipa Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kew 74024.100HR* — Photograph. 2067×2835. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. *Helikewisia roseatulipa* wb. Amy.C., 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** b27c74a092a9222518bb154f79468dd3caa0dd7f894dcdfd3730113885008202
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V2-1.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326181302/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V2-1.jpg?v=1680151814>

Diagnosis: *Helikewisia roseatulipa* is characterized by its fabric pattern of pink tulips and green leaves against a white background and its ventral medial row of 15 shank button with no thread holes, with a wood-like surface.

Etymology: Portmanteau of Latin *rosea*, feminine form of *roseus* (“pink”) + *Tulipa* L.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.3.2 *Helikewisia amyboria*

Helikewisia amyboria Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: Kew 9018.1728, person on left. See Section 6.2.

Diagnosis: *Helikewisia amyboria* is characterized by its fabric pattern of trees with pink trunks and slight potato/brown/golden-colored leaves, and clouds and a ventral medial row of 15 circular buttons with four thread holes.

Etymology: Blend of *Amy* + Latin *arbor* (“tree”), as *Helikewisia arbor* is already used.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.4 Genus *Kewbellothea*

Kewbellothea Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewbellothea* is characterized by origin from the sleeved variant of the Kewbello pattern; phenetically, the combination of the Kew tea dress bodice and Portobello trousers; and the presence of a dorsal medial zipper on the bodice. Bilateral ventral darts present from the third button to the bodice–skirt seam; bilateral sets of three seams at outward flare angle; bilateral pockets.

Remarks: There exist two phylogenetic pathways through which a tea dress Kewbello may arise; from the Kewbello pattern itself (pathway 1), or an independent recombination of the Kew tea dress bodice and the Portobello trousers, done without referencing the pattern (pathway 2). Pathway 2 remains unattested.

Type species: *Kewbellothea aquacolor* (see Section 4.6.1)

4.5 *Kewbellothea* subg. *Expansa*

Kewbellothea subgenus *Expansa* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewbellothea* subg. *Expansa* is defined by origin from size 21 and above of the Kewbello pattern. See Chang-Smith (2026d).

Etymology: From Latin *expansa*, feminine form of *expansus* (“expanded”), referring to the pattern’s expanded size range..

Type species: *Kewbellothea mottramia* (see Section 4.5.1)

4.5.1 *Kewbellothea mottramia*

Kewbellothea mottramia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: Mottram 4958.194 — Photograph. 1200×1646. Ventral view. Subject’s arms fully adducted. Hair positioned dorsally, dress unobscured. Outdoor lighting conditions, daytime; wooden building in background; dog in bottom right of image. *Kewbellothea mottramia* wb. Eleanor.M., unknown. © Eleanor Mottram or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026d)
- **SHA2-256:** 3087d2aeaacba1075e2653eaf93d5f5b09f7bc6467a1d696ddb792696f012433
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/NinaLeeKewbelloJumpsuitEleanorMottram.jpg?v=1696062971>

- **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171751/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/NinaLeeKewbelloJumpsuitEleanorMottram.jpg?v=1696062971>

Diagnosis: *Kewbellothea mottramia* is characterized by its olive-green-like color and ventral medial row of six circular vaguely green/gray buttons on the bodice.

Etymology: From *Mottram* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.5.2 *Kewbellothea lavendula*

Kewbellothea lavendula Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kewbello* 67208.705 — Photograph. 3024×4032. Ventral view. Subject’s arms embedded in bilateral pockets. Taken outdoors during the day. Subject standing in shadow of building with plants in background. Hair terminates at roughly chin level; garment not obscured. *Kewbellothea lavendula* wb. unknown. © unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026d)
- **SHA2-256:** 0623aff976e9cecdc83b18a3a282202b3cc61e5300ecdc51e4b8ecb7977bedeb
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 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171751/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/image_67208705.jpg?v=1696875452

Diagnosis: *Kewbellothea lavendula* is characterized by its floral fabric, with a lavender background, multiple flowers, of which a red flower is highly prominent, with subtle cyan leaves.

Etymology: From Medieval Latin *lavendula* (“lavender”), from the lavender background of the fabric.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.5.3 *Kewbellothea rubera*

Kewbellothea rubera Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kewbello* 27874.191 — Photograph. 2268×3024. EXIF metadata stripped. Angled right ventral view. Subject’s right arm on lateral end of waist. Hair positioned ventrally. Visibility of ventral medial button row significantly impeded by angle of bodice and pattern camouflage. *Kewbellothea rubera* wb. unknown. © or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026d)
- **SHA2-256:** 44a7d4f367d05f99db018a2a05fbf073886efca20d4bf1d38fe8d97e73e308a9
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/20230910_191020_resized.jpg?v=1696875452
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171826/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/20230910_191020_resized.jpg?v=1696875452

Diagnosis: *Kewbellothea rubera* is characterized by a dorsal medial zipper that terminates at the bodice–skirt seam, a ventral medial button row, and a fabric with a red background with a leopard-like pattern of black and pink shapes, some of which superficially resemble human faces.

Etymology: From Latin *rubera*, corrupted form of *rubra*, feminine form of *ruber* (“red”).

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Kewbello* 27874.236 — Photograph. 2268×3024. EXIF metadata stripped. Dorsal view. Subject’s arms fully adducted. Hair positioned ventrally. *Kewbellothea rubera* wb. unknown. © unknown photographer, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:**

- **SHA2-256:** cd6b38f3dd7750cae473f395d6e6ae21807f636e8647c37c9873776988c5d808
- **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/20230910_190855_resized.jpg?v=1696875452
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/20230910_190855_resized.jpg?v=1696875452

4.6 *Kewbellothea* subg. *Ninae*

Kewbellothea subgenus *Ninae* Lemuria, 2026

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewbellothea* subg. *Ninae* is defined by having been created by Nina Chang-Smith.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*.

Type species: *Kewbellothea autumn* (see Section 4.6.2)

4.6.1 *Kewbellothea aquacolor*

Kewbellothea aquacolor Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Nina* 90184.113 — Photograph. 3000×4114. *Kewbellothea aquacolor* wb. *Nina*, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026e)
- **SHA2-256:** aa9b9813b98b284c9aba1df3deaa3f0d1e430b499674060f1b047ce070eaaad05
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_purple_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_purple_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174

Diagnosis: *Kewbellothea aquacolor* is characterized by its watercolor-like fabric, with a blue background and subtle purple shades; and a ventral medial button row of five circular blue buttons with four thread-holes.

Etymology: From Latin *aqua* (“water”) + *color* (“color”); “watercolor”, from the similarity of the fabric to watercolor.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Nina* 90184.148 — Photograph. 3000×4114. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewbellothea aquacolor* wb. *Nina*, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:**
 - **SHA2-256:** 47756822208f53a8ae585e460ae7036811ddf0ab88dc9db7347422cb5876e52f
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_purple_background_c3.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171821/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_purple_background_c3.jpg
- *Nina* 90184.761 — Photograph. 3000×4114. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewbellothea aquacolor* wb. *Nina*, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:**
 - **SHA2-256:** a5676cb8be0f0537dd26f6c02a0bd046212af4b432990817a4e981e422bd0364
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_back_view_purple_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/Nina_Lee_Kewbello_with_sleeves_back_view_purple_background_v2.jpg?v=1722462174

4.6.2 *Kewbellothea autumnna*

Kewbellothea autumnna Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Nina* 90340.105 — Photograph. 2400×2954. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewbellothea autumnna* wb. Nina, unknown. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026e)
- **SHA2-256:** 274e7dbc7069f80d1cb77451eb2a5a1125578e73901f51e5cf09cee74751200f
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/NinaLeeKewbelloJumpsuitautumnv1.jpg?v=1722462287>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260405171750/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/files/NinaLeeKewbelloJumpsuitautumnv1.jpg?v=1722462287>

Diagnosis: *Kewbellothea autumnna* is characterized by its maroon-background fabric with floral patterns. Orange, pink, and white flowers, with berry-like fruits, colored blue. No known correspondence to biological taxa.

Etymology: From Latin *autumna* (“autumn”), due to the autumn-like colors of the fabric and the holotype image.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.7 Genus *Kewisia*

Kewisia Lemuria, 2026

See Lemuria (2026)

4.8 *Kewisia* subg. *Ninae*

Kewisia subg. *Ninae* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewisia* subg. *Ninae* is defined by origin from Nina Chang-Smith or a close relative.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

4.8.1 *Kewisia tropiki*

Kewisia tropiki Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Nina* 2017.013.8377KT — Photograph. 3543×5313. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Subject standing at angle. Hair positioned laterally and draping ventrally, right strap obscured. *Kewisia tropiki* wb. Nina, c. 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 42929bfbdf49b423201a3650623216e0cb08cbc41299a1c6f8b555f68ff5fea7
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-V2-Nina-1.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20230714101532/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-V2-Nina-1.jpg?v=1680151814>

Diagnosis: *Kewisia tropiki* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 15 circular two thread-hole buttons of a primarily ivory color with slight dark blue accents at random angles, and a consistent vertical threadline; and a fabric with a pink background with blue leaves, and red and purple flowers, the “Tropical Stems” fabric from Lady McElroy.

Etymology:

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Kew* 4557.234 (see Section 6.2)

4.8.2 *Kewisia roseafolia*

Kewisia roseafolia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Nina 2017.013.8289KR* — Photograph. 1937×2657. EXIF metadata stripped. Angled ventral view. Subject's hair positioned laterally, obscuring her left strap. *Kewisia roseafolia* wb. Nina, 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** f4c34767bc2a237da8cfd304e052e3dfa7b97ee57dc0feba8116c11e00405f0a
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V2-9.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326192109/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V2-9.jpg?v=1680151814>

Diagnosis: *Kewisia roseafolia* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 15 circular two thread-hole buttons of a wooden color, and a fabric with stylized depictions of leaves in pink and white.

Etymology: From Latin *rosea*, feminine form of *roseus* “pink, rose-colored” + *folia*, pseudo-Latin feminine form of *folium* “leaf”.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.9 Genus *Kewisicasa*

Kewisicasa Lemuria, 2026; gen. nov.

Type species: *Kewisicasa laria* (see Section 4.9.1)

Description: Ventral medial row of 10 buttons. First buttonhole horizontal, others vertical. Seam across entire skirt between first and second buttons. Slight flare, no higher than ~20°. ³ Terminates roughly at knee-level. Slight drape at inferior end.

Remarks: Though we named the genus *Kewisicasa* in Lemuria (2026), we did not formally describe it. We now do so here.

4.9.1 *Kewisicasa laria*

Kewisicasa laria Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kew 14201.147KL* — Photograph. 2067×2835. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. White sleeveless shirt tucked underneath skirt. *Kewisicasa laria* wb. Amy.C., 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 00067336936823f5c556ec1e2a2796618d300d6becdc6b1d94b6f7b1ddacdf9d
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V3-3.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260327013520/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V3-3.jpg?v=1680151814>

Diagnosis: *Kewisicasa laria* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 10 buttons, white background with two thread holes; and a sky blue fabric with seagull-like shapes.

Etymology: Pseudo-Latin feminine form of *larus* (“gull”), from the genus *Larus* Linnaeus, 1758.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.

³For the purposes of defining flare, the silhouette of the fabric is measured, with the inferiormost end being considered north. The wearer is then assumed to be in the standard anatomical position with their head facing downwards; their left is considered 270° and their right is considered 90°.

- **Kew 14201.158KL** — Photograph. 2067×2835. EXIF metadata stripped. Dorsal view. White sleeveless shirt tucked underneath skirt. *Kewisicasa laria* wb. Amy.C., 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
 - **SHA2-256:** cb235a00a36a79798756de3885310b8469e53fe867fbf52a8fb3d9506b47f782
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V3-4.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260327013518/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V3-4.jpg?v=1680151814>

4.10 *Kewisicasa* subg. *Expansa*

Kewisicasa subg. *Expansa* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewisicasa* subg. *Expansa* is defined by origin from size 21 and above of the standalone straight skirt (*Kewisicasa*) variant of the Kew pattern.

Etymology: From Latin *expansa*, feminine form of *expansus* (“expanded”), referring to the larger size range.

4.10.1 *Kewisicasa jessae*

Kewisicasa jessae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Jess 29081.31.58KJ* — Photograph. 1440×1440. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Ventral medial button row unobscured. Hair terminates significantly superior to skirt. Visibility not obscured. *Kewisicasa jessae* wb. Jess (W/2026 F9), unknown. © Unknown photographer, unknown, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 9899938117bf4ffa79c03e6c6b80b4e998351f716eb010e74dbe1dca808f3125
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Jess-Nina-Lee-Kew-Skirt-16-28.jpg?v=1677871695>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260330022036/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Jess-Nina-Lee-Kew-Skirt-16-28.jpg?v=1677871695>

Diagnosis: *Kewisicasa jessae* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 11 buttons, white background and unknown black pattern, and an unknown amount of threadholes; and a plain magenta fabric. Slightly larger vertical gap between the first, second, and third buttons.

Etymology: *Jess* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

4.10.2 *Kewisicasa mandia*

Kewisicasa mandia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Mandy 210535.158.3903KM* — Photograph. 1658×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Subject looking upward. Drape of skirt obscures inferior portion of ventral medial button row. Arms extended outward. *Kewisicasa mandia* wb. Mandy (W/2026 F10), unknown. © Unknown photographer, unknown, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 459b5efb70c21f871d81205fbf51142631984ca4f8fdb03be464f10dc794442f
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Mandy-Nina-Lee-Kew-Skirt-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260330021938/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Mandy-Nina-Lee-Kew-Skirt-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>

Diagnosis: *Kewisicasa mandia* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 11 buttons, white with two threadholes; and a green fabric with a grid of white lines.

Etymology: *Mandy* + *-ia*, feminine abstract noun suffix.

4.10.3 *Kewisicasa apprichia*

Kewisicasa apprichia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Apprich* 48183.493KA — Photograph. 1200×1600. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. *Kewisicasa apprichia* wb. Emily.Ap., c. 2021. © Emily Apprich or unknown photographer, unknown year, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026c)
- **SHA2-256:** c5876e74a42dc028086fe963b1adacd5ef501ae0653418c4313a9bb09988ed28
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Emily-Apprich-Kew-Expansion-pack-16-28-straight-skirt-10.jpg?v=1677871708>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260403143809/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Emily-Apprich-Kew-Expansion-pack-16-28-straight-skirt-10.jpg?v=1677871708>

Diagnosis: *Kewisicasa apprichia* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 11 buttons, green and yellow with mixed colors, with a slightly larger gap between the first and second buttons; and a plain black fabric.

Etymology: *Apprich* + *-ia*.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.10.4 *Kewisicasa argenta*

Kewisicasa argenta Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Srebrenka* 20180.118KA — Photograph. 1920×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Subject holding stick in left hand. *Kewisicasa argenta* wb. Silverluna, c. 2021. © Srebrenka/Silverluna/sewsilverluna888 or unknown photographer, unknown year, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Chang-Smith (2026c) and Silverluna and Chang-Smith (2021)
- **SHA2-256:** 13463549148161ed83df081566e69ce421d0acaf9d54c9382ad2b2c767f48247
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Srebrenka-Kapica-Kew-Expansion-pack-16-28-straight-skirt-1-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260403143813/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Srebrenka-Kapica-Kew-Expansion-pack-16-28-straight-skirt-1-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>

Diagnosis: *Kewisicasa argenta* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 13 buttons, black with four thread holes, inconsistently spaced; and a navy-blue military camouflage-like pixel fabric, vaguely resembling ocean waves, with the small letters “OSRM” or “OSBM” scattered across the pattern. One of the most distinct shapes is one resembling the outline of Croatia’s borders, in the lightest blue color.

Remarks:

- The shape of Croatia appearing on the fabric may be unintentional on the designer’s part in designing the fabric, or on Srebrenka’s part in choosing the fabric. This may be a form of pareidolia, further reinforced by our knowledge of Srebrenka’s origin from the Balkans.
- Due to political sensitivities regarding the countries in the Balkans, we are unable to speculate on Srebrenka’s home country beyond a general guess of “the Balkans”.

Etymology: From Latin *argenta* (“silver”), from the first fragment of Silverluna’s alias, *silver*.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.11 *Kewthea*

Kewthea Lemuria, 2026

See Lemuria (2026)

4.12 *Kewthea* subg. *Ninae*

Kewthea subg. *Ninae* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewthea* subg. *Ninae* is defined by origin from Nina Chang-Smith or a close relative.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.12.1 *Kewthea ruberabotonia*

Kewthea ruberabotonia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kew* 4109.187KR — Photograph. 3543×5315. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Subject's hair positioned ventrally on her right. *Kewthea ruberabotonia* wb. Amy.C. (W/2026 F7), c. 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 4b13414afd28f3149ae852081a83dddc00f48b53e2263023726a7405762143ef
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-V1-Amy-close-up-1.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20230714160745/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-V1-Amy-close-up-1.jpg?v=1680151814>

Diagnosis: *Kewthea ruberabotonia* is characterized by a ventral medial row of red buttons, plastic, with two thread holes, and a fabric with a white background and multiple unidentified plants.

Etymology: From pseudo-Latin *rubera*, corrupted form of *rubra*, feminine form of *ruber* (“red”). Also interpretable as *ruber* (“red”) + *-a-* (epenthetic vowel added for euphony) + *botonia* (“button”).

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.12.2 *Kewthea venetaflora*

Kewthea venetaflora Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Kew* 4109.124KV — Photograph. 1937×2657. EXIF metadata stripped. Angled ventral view. Subject's hair positioned entirely dorsally. Subject facing to her right (relative to camera, from her perspective). *Kewthea venetaflora* wb. Amy.C. (W/2026 F7), c. 2017. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
- **SHA2-256:** 6d12a063eead31810dde4f7dbac040cf5e7fd1ba25d1fd5f601d21c2d4e3b378
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V1-4.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326181258/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Kew-Dress-V1-4.jpg?v=1680151814>

Etymology: From Latin *veneta*, feminine form of *venetus* (“sky blue”) + pseudo-Latin *flora* “flower”, from Latin *Flora*, the goddess of flowers.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13 *Kewthea* subg. *Expansa*

Kewthea subg. *Expansa* Lemuria, 2026; subgen. nov.

Diagnosis: Phylogenetically, *Kewthea* subg. *Expansa* is defined by origin from size 21 and above of the tea dress (*Kewthidae*) variant of the *Kew* pattern.

Etymology: From Latin *expansa*, feminine form of *expansus* (“expanded”), referring to the larger size range.

4.13.1 *Kewthea hawkinsia*

Kewthea hawkinsia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Laura* 2023.001.1682KH — Photograph. 1871×2551. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, bilaterally obscuring certain parts of neckline. Skirt deliberately held out with hand. *Kewthea hawkinsia* wb. Laura.Haw., 2023. © Laura Hawkins or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026a)
- **SHA2-256:** e56fa1e776eb9a6cba4e98059778e9df903ab31613e39ad7c72422d4374dfe39
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Hawkins-Kew-Dress.jpg?v=1677871695>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326050209/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Hawkins-Kew-Dress.jpg?v=1677871695>

Diagnosis: *K. hawkinsia* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 15 heart-shaped two thread-hole buttons, and a fabric with a light white–pink background and a stylized red flower with two petals and black dots scattered in a roughly rectangular shape with curved edges.

Etymology: From *Hawkins* + *-ia*, feminine abstract noun suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13.2 *Kewthea caledonia*

Kewthea caledonia Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Emma* 2023.001.1402KC — Photograph. 1440×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Indoors. Hair positioned ventrally, bilaterally obscuring certain parts of neckline. *Kewthea caledonia* wb. Emma (W/2026 F5), c. 2023. © Emma or unknown photographer, c. 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026a)
- **SHA2-256:** 4e650f4804476216e169e757f5eef9a9fb87279ebda2e477b8bbc0b5e59644f
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Sew-Do-It-Emma-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326051449/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Sew-Do-It-Emma-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>

Diagnosis: *K. caledonia* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of ~15 small buttons,⁴ and a fabric with a dark-blue background and numerous variably-sized sky blue, purple, and pale bright orange dots scattered at random.

Etymology: From Latin *Caledonia* (“Scotland”), from Emma’s location.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13.3 *Kewthea glaciesedulis*

Kewthea glaciesedulis Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Laura* 20710.583KG — Photograph. 2560×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Outdoors. Hair positioned ventrally, bilaterally obscuring certain parts of neckline. In left hand, subject holding object similar to “ice cream cone”; with a conical cardboard material representing the “cone” and a ball of yarn representing the “ice cream”. *Kewthea glaciesedulis* wb. Laura.Haw., c. 2023. © Laura Hawkins or unknown photographer, c. 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026c)
- **SHA2-256:** adeab545bfd020f27e3900970327930d25ffb1c51b319bfe752cc209d5d41872
- **Raw image URLs:**

⁴Image resolution insufficient to identify buttons.

- **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Hawkins-Specky-Seamstress-Kew-Expansion-16-28-gathered-skirt-1-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>
- **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260405161421/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Hawkins-Specky-Seamstress-Kew-Expansion-16-28-gathered-skirt-1-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>

Diagnosis: *K. glaciesedulis* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 15 white buttons; and a fabric with a white background with a pattern of ice cream cones; consisting of cyan-colored ice cream in a cone drawn with black lines.

Etymology: From Latin *glacies* (“ice”) + *edulis* (“edible”), literally “edible ice”. Translation sourced from Wiktionary.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13.4 *Kewthea eleanorae*

Kewthea eleanorae Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Eleanor* 2023.001.8404KE — Photograph. 1440×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewthea eleanorae* wb. Eleanor (W/2026 F3), c. 2023. © Eleanor or unknown photographer, c. 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026a)
- **SHA2-256:** e15a799d0f7b20bc03da95bfcf0cf0f8fed33443fa70cda44bbf35bba2265bdd
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Eleanor-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326051053/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Eleanor-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871695>

Diagnosis: *K. eleanorae* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 10 circular buttons with no thread holes, four on the bodice and six on the skirt; and a plain dark blue fabric.

Etymology: From *Eleanor* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13.5 *Kewthea lauraflora*

Kewthea lauraflora Lemuria, 2026; sp. nov.

Holotype: *Laura* 2023.001.4901KL — Photograph. 1920×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewthea lauraflora* wb. Laura (W/2026 F4), c. 2023. © Laura or unknown photographer, c. 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026a)
- **SHA2-256:** e03d4374644fb22f63d97ccc4d5ca523f35889c85666bda316040e7174ec3404
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326192448/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Laura-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-16-28-scaled.jpg>

Diagnosis: *K. lauraflora* is characterized by a ventral medial button row of 13 circular purple buttons with a primarily purple floral pattern.

Etymology: From *Laura* + pseudo-Latin *flora*, to distinguish from *Kewthea hawkinsia* wb. Laura.Haw., from Latin *Flora*, the goddess of flowers.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

5 General remarks

At least two distinct persons appear in the official product photography for Chang-Smith (2026b), with the exception of pattern testers. We were able to identify the first person as Nina Chang-Smith herself.

The second person, the one wearing *Kewisicasa laria*, was slightly harder to identify; but we believe the person's name to be Amy Chang, based on (1) the filename for *Kew* 4109.187KR being "Kew-V1-Amy-close-up-1.jpg", and (2) the presence of the name *Amy Chang* on seating chart signage for Chang-Smith's June 2019 wedding (Chang-Smith 2020b, ninth image on page).

We were able to infer Silverluna's name as being *Srebrenka Kapica* based on image filenames.

6 Appendix

6.1 Person abbreviations

The abbreviations **Nina** for Nina Chang-Smith and **Lemuria** for Lemuria have been defined in Lemuria (2026).

In this paper, we establish the new person abbreviations:

- **Laura.Haw.** — Laura Hawkins (W/2026 F6), pattern tester for the *Kew* expansion pack
- **Amy.C.** — Amy Chang (W/2026 F7), relative of Nina Chang-Smith
- **Silverluna** — Srebrenka Kapica (Instagram: @sewsilverluna888; W/2026 G1), sewist from Europe (nationality unknown; possibly the Balkans)
- **Emily.Ap.** — Emily Apprich (W/2026 G2), pattern tester.

We establish the new alphanumeric designations:

- **Eleanor** (W/2026 F3), wearer of *Kewthea eleanorae*

6.2.1 New image specimens

These image specimens do not correspond to one singular taxon.

- *Kew* 9018.1728 (a.k.a. *Kew* 4557.234) — Photograph. 3361×4618. EXIF metadata stripped. On left, Amy Chang, standing, facing camera, hair positioned laterally, partial obscuration of straps; on right, Nina Chang-Smith, facing camera, hair positioned laterally, straps minimally obscured. Both standing at angles relative to camera. Inferior-most button of *Helikewisia amyboria* unfastened. Left: *Helikewisia amyboria* wb. Amy.C, 2017; right: *Kewisia tropiki* wb. Nina, 2017; © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, c. 2017, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 2cf4fe38ca4e664c8a05a60ca0b3b203d7b672f6988e530f0186e724938ae614
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/NinaLeeKewDressversion1.jpg?v=1680151814>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260326190410/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/product/s/NinaLeeKewDressversion1.jpg?v=1680151814>

- **Laura** (W/2026 F4), wearer of *Kewthea lauraflora*
- **Emma** (W/2026 F5), wearer of *Kewthea caledonia*
- **Jess** (W/2026 F9), wearer of *Kewisicasa jessae*
- **Mandy** (W/2026 F10), wearer of *Kewisicasa mandia*

6.2 Image specimens

We used the following image specimen identifiers:

- *Apprich* 48183.493KA
- *Eleanor* 2023.001.8404KE
- *Emma* 2023.001.1402KC
- *Jess* 29081.31.58KJ
- *Kew* 14201.147KL
- *Kew* 14201.158KL
- *Kew* 4109.124KV
- *Kew* 4109.187KR
- *Kew* 74024.100HR
- *Kew* 9018.1728 (*Kew* 4557.234)
- *Kewbello* 27874.191
- *Kewbello* 27874.236
- *Kewbello* 67208.705
- *Laura* 2023.001.1682KH
- *Laura* 2023.001.4901KL
- *Laura* 20710.583KG
- *Mandy* 210535.158.3903KM
- *Mottram* 4958.194
- *Nina* 2017.013.8289KR
- *Nina* 2017.013.8377KT
- *Nina* 90184.113
- *Nina* 90184.148
- *Nina* 90184.761
- *Nina* 90340.105
- *Nina* 90381.248
- *Nina* 90381.276
- *Nina* 90387.475
- *Nina* 90387.478
- *Srebrenka* 20180.118KA

6.3 Acknowledgements

We used R; specifically, `ggtree`, to render tree figures. For information on `ggtree`, see Yu, Smith, Zhu, Guan, and Lam (2017).

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6.4 Data availability

Supplementary data, such as the `.yml` file containing structured data for *Kewbellothea*; and the raw standalone Newick tree, are made available on Zenodo.

6.5 Information

Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy is the gray literature journal of the First Lemurian Clothing Taxonomy, a system by Lemuria to assign Latin names to dresses using biological methods. The author, known mononymically as just Lemuria, is a Filipino programmer and independent gray literature researcher from Manila.

Disclaimer: *Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy* is a non-peer-reviewed, single-author, citizen science/gray literature publication with no institutional backing.

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- Visit us at: <https://lct01.lemuria.ph>
- Version control: <https://github.com/a-random-lemurian/lct01.lemuria.ph>
- Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/communities/lct01>

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